

NOvA's Current and Future Sterile Neutrino Searches

NuPhys 2026

ν_s

Adam Lister, 7th January 2026

Ash River, MN

Functionally identical Near and Far detectors

- * Extruded PVC cells filled with liquid scintillator
- * Segmented tracking calorimeters

FD - 14 kT
344,064 channels

ND - 0.3 kT
20,192 channels

Fermilab, IL

To APD

Flavia told you about NOvA's 3F oscillation program earlier in this session
[[Flavia Cicala, "Neutrino Oscillations" session, ~30 mins ago](#)]

3F Oscillations: The Full Picture?

It's not clear that it is!

NOvA has a broad program looking for new physics in neutrino oscillations and beyond

This talk focuses on one possible extension - **sterile neutrinos**

Well Established Anomalies

each well described by oscillations with $\Delta m^2 \sim 1\text{eV}^2 - 10\text{eV}^2$

LSND/MiniBooNE

$\nu_e/\bar{\nu}_e$ Appearance

Gallium Experiments (SAGE/GALLEX/BEST)

ν_e Disappearance

IceCube

ν_μ Disappearance

A (Non-Exhaustive) Timeline of Sterile Neutrino Searches

ANOMALIES

NOT ANOMALIES

LEGEND $\bar{\nu}_e \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_e$ $\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e$ $\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_e$ $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_\mu$

NC

**No NC disappearance
expected under 3F model**

NC

ν_μ

No NC disappearance
expected under 3F model

Looking for disappearance above
that expected from 3F oscillations

NC

ν_μ

No NC disappearance expected under 3F model

Looking for disappearance above that expected from 3F oscillations

Jointly fit neutrino-mode NC and ν_μ data in both detectors under a 3+1 model

Complementary to short-baseline ν_e appearance searches!

Two independent analyses with different approaches

Under 3F assumption

$$\Delta m_{31}^2 = 2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{eV}^2$$

$$\theta_{23} = 49.6^\circ$$

Good agreement between two analyses

Consistent with 3F oscillations at 90% Confidence Level

World-leading limits at high Δm_{41}^2

High $\Delta m_{41}^2 \rightarrow$ rapid oscillations.

Near Detector O(millions) events, systematically limited

Low $\Delta m_{41}^2 \rightarrow$ slower oscillations.

Far Detector O(100s) events, statistically limited

We also presented limits in terms of $\sin^2 \theta_{34}$ and

$$\sin^2 2\theta_{\mu\tau} = \sin^2 2\theta_{24} \sin^2 \theta_{34}$$

PRL 134 (2025) 8, 081804

Upcoming analysis will use 2x neutrino-mode data, NOvA's antineutrino-mode dataset, and a ν -on-e sample as an in-situ beam constraint*. **Results expected 2026!**

... but how do we go beyond this?

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... but how do we go beyond this?

**All NOvA beam analyses to date
have used the NuMI beamline**

There is another

NOvA has been taking BNB data since 2015 in the ND
 Collected around 2.5×10^{20} POT

Longest running After MiniBooNE!

	NuMI	BNB
Protons Per Pulse	5e13	5e12
Rep Rate (Hz)	<1	5
Proton Energy (GeV)	120	8
Off-axis angle (°)	0.8	9.24
Baseline (km)	~1	~0.768

NOvA - FNAL E929
 Run: 14025 / 0
 Event: 1854 / NuMI
 UTC Mon Feb 15, 2021
 20:13:37.809773376

NOvA - FNAL E929
 Run: 16154 / 5
 Event: 107027 / BnB
 UTC Tue Dec 10, 2024
 22:43:2.551923008

NOvA - FNAL E929
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Flux prediction translated from original MiniBooNE flux files

Thank You to the MiniBooNE collaboration!

NOvA Simulation

Peak pion energy shifts down
 $\sim 600 \text{ MeV} \rightarrow \sim 200 \text{ MeV}$

Reduced high-energy tail for K^+ ,
 becomes peaked around 1.4 GeV

NOvA Simulation

Early stages of developing this sample.

Currently simulation suggests > 5000 selected neutrinos (only contained shown),

Low energy peak from neutrinos from pions largely diminished due to **cross-section effects** and **low selection efficiency below 500 MeV** - **potential for improvements here, additional optimisations in progress**

NOvA Simulation

The BNB-only sensitivity is **comparable to the NuMI Near Detector samples** below $\log_{10} \Delta m_{41}^2 \lesssim 0.5$

BNB can only be seen by the NOvA Near Detector
here we compare the sensitivity to the other NuMI ND samples

NOvA Simulation

The BNB-only sensitivity is **comparable to the NuMI Near Detector samples** below $\log_{10} \Delta m_{41}^2 \lesssim 0.5$

Full analysis Asimov sensitivity shows around a 25% improvement in sensitivity

NOvA Simulation

Summary

- NOvA's most recently published sterile neutrino search is world leading in some regions of parameter space.
- An updated analysis, using 2x the neutrino-mode dataset, NOvA's antineutrino dataset, and a ν -on-e sample, is being prepared, and is expected in 2026.
- Beyond this we are looking to improve our analysis by incorporating our sample from a second beamline, the BNB. First sensitivities suggest around a 25% gain in sensitivity. **This will also improve the robustness of the analysis!**
- We're also exploring other ways to improve our sterile neutrino searches - **look out for more from us in the future!**

Thanks for Listening!

Additional Slides

The NOvA detectors are **optimised** for surface running in a 2 GeV beam!

NOvA - FNAL E929

Run: 18620 / 13

Event: 178402 / --

UTC Fri Jan 9, 2015

00:13:53.087341608

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Consistent with 3F oscillations at 90% Confidence Level

Most of our sensitivity to θ_{34} comes from **FD NC sample**, we are statistically limited across the full space.

First limits for $\Delta m_{41}^2 < 0.1 \text{ eV}^2$

Consistent with 3F oscillations at 90% Confidence Level

$$\sin^2 2\theta_{\mu\mu} = 4 \cos^2 \theta_{13} \sin^2 \theta_{24} (1 - \cos^2 \theta_{14} \sin^2 \theta_{24})$$

$$\sin^2 2\theta_{\mu e} = \sin^2 2\theta_{14} \sin^2 \theta_{24}$$

$$\sin^2 2\theta_{ee} = \sin^2 2\theta_{14}$$

$$\sin^2 2\theta_{\mu\tau} = \sin^2 2\theta_{24} \sin^2 \theta_{34}$$

Largest systematic uncertainties from **Cross-sections**, and **flux**

NOvA Preliminary

Does The Flux Pass The Smell Test?

Two-body decay dominant for π/K decays

Effectively no relationship between parent energy and neutrino energy above some threshold

Contained

Uncontained

Why Should This Work?

Nominal simulation with a ~10% error, with some shape

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You open the box on the (fake) data

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Systematic uncertainty or **Sterile neutrinos?**

Why Should This Work?

BNB has different baseline, oscillations show up in a different place

Data looks more like systematic uncertainty than oscillations!

Why Should This Work?

Incompatible with systematic uncertainties, fit as oscillations!

Why Should This Work?

Oscillations go as L/E , systematic uncertainties don't have an L dependence.

... but only works if you have

Correlated uncertainties

For BNB/NuMI neutrinos of a given energy:

- **Cross-section uncertainties should be very correlated** (up to selection effects) ✓
- **Detector uncertainties should be very correlated** (up to angular/selection effects) ✓
- **Beam uncertainties** are complicated, there should be correlations in hadron production, but very different beam energies, different target (material and geometry) ✗ mean the uncertainties can be **treated as uncorrelated**.

... and with Electron Neutrinos?

Neutrino beams not pure ν_μ , also some ν_e component, and both undergo oscillations

Toy study

10,000 total neutrinos, split with a ratio

$$N_{\nu_\mu} : N_{\nu_e} = 0.99 : 0.01$$

At some point in parameter space, **disappearance of beam ν_e** equivalent to **$\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$ appearance**

$$P_{\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e} \propto \sin^2 2\theta_{ee} = \sin^2 2\theta_{14}$$

$$P_{\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e} \propto \sin^2 2\theta_{\mu e} = \sin^2 2\theta_{14} \sin^2 \theta_{24}$$

Happens when
$$\frac{N_{\nu_e}}{N_{\nu_e} + N_{\nu_\mu}} = \sin^2 \theta_{24}$$

... and with Electron Neutrinos?

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Second beamline with different ν_e fraction breaks this degeneracy